

Square transposition: an approach to the transposition process in block cipher

Magdalena A. Ineke Pekereng, Alz Danny Wowor

Department of Informatic Engineering, Universitas Kristen Satya Wacana, Salatiga, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The transposition process is needed in cryptography to create a diffusion effect on data encryption standard (DES) and advanced encryption standard (AES) algorithms as standard information security algorithms by the National Institute of Standards and Technology. The problem with DES and AES algorithms is that their transposition index values form patterns and do not form random values. This condition will certainly make it easier for a cryptanalyst to look for a relationship between ciphertexts because some processes are predictable. This research designs a transposition algorithm called square transposition. Each process uses square 8×8 as a place to insert and retrieve 64-bits. The determination of the pairing of the input scheme and the retrieval scheme that have unequal flow is an important factor in producing a good transposition. The square transposition can generate random and non-pattern indices so that transposition can be done better than DES and AES.

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Corresponding Author:

Magdalena A. Ineke Pekereng

Department of Informatics Engineering

Universitas Kristen Satya Wacana

Jl. Notohamidjojo 1-10, Salatiga 50718, Indonesia

Email: ineke.pakereng@uksw.edu

1. INTRODUCTION

Diffusional transposition process is useful for the spread of plaintext redundancy in a ciphertext. Modern cryptography such as data encryption standard (DES) and advanced encryption standard (AES) as information security standards used by National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) also contain transposition as one of the important processes in the algorithm [1], [2]. DES with initial permutation (IP) and inverse initial permutation (IP)⁻¹ are truly essential in the transposition process [3]. Whereas, AES with shift rows capability is simpler in transposition [4]. The two algorithms use index values to determine the shift of each object. The excess diffusion in the algorithm is one of the factors that make DES and AES still attractive and feasible to use, which makes both of them are chosen by researchers as their information security methods [5]-[21].

The DES transposition index value in Figure 1 shows patterned results. 64-bit outputs in DES always form 8-bit groups. Each eight index values produce the same pattern, starting from the highest value that gradually decreases. For example a_i as the index value where ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 8$) in the first group, the value of the same position in the next group always becomes $a_i + 1 \pmod{64}$.

The transposition on AES also has a patterned index value as shown in Figure 2. The AES index value forms a group of 4 characters. The first group (4-0) consists of four upward histograms and 0 different

histograms. The second group: (3-1) consists of three upward histograms and 1 histogram that has different values. The same condition applies to the third group (2-2) and the fourth group (1-3).

The index value is expected as a new position to make the sequence of each character to be more irregular so that the diffusion factor will increasingly appear in the ciphertext. The moving of objects based on index values in DES and AES indicates a problem because it forms a certain pattern. The problem in DES and AES is that when the sequence or pattern of data $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ is known, the probability for finding the $\{n+1, n+2, \dots\}$ data is great. This will weaken the algorithm and the patterned condition will certainly make it easier for cryptanalysts to find a plaintext-ciphertext relationship because part of the process is predictable.

A study related to the transposition process was also carried out by [22]-[25], who dismissed the shift row operation as a transposition operation in AES cryptography. Thus, XOR as an additional operation can be performed repeatedly up to three times. The research done by [26], [27] adds various processes to correct the shortcomings of transposition in the algorithm. Although the improvement of the transposition process by adding the algorithm in parallel will certainly obtain a good result, the adding of the algorithm takes more time, and space. In terms of efficiency, the algorithm is less elegant to be used as information security.

Figure 1. Index values of DES transposition

Figure 2. Index values of AES transposition

This research designs a transposition algorithm called Square Transposition. A square of $n \times n$ size is used as the medium to hold ($m = n \times n$)-bit. Each bit input is entered into a square using certain rules and taking of bit is also done with certain rules. Determination of whether the designed algorithm is good or not is seen based on its statistical testing. Statistical testing is done to determine the randomness of each index value. In addition, correlation testing is used to measure the algorithm's ability to disguise the relationship between input and output. Finally, DES and AES are compared to find out the power of Square Transposition in the algorithm for the transposition process.

2. PROPOSED RESEARCH

2.1. Square transposition

Square transposition consists of two processes namely bit-input into a square and bit-retrieval with a certain predetermined size. Suppose $T = \text{text input}$, $t_i = i\text{-th text character}$ and $a_i = i\text{-th binary character}$, then:

$$T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}; \quad n|8, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad (1)$$

Where, $t_1 = \{a_{01}, a_{02}, a_{03}, \dots, a_{08}\}$, $t_2 = \{a_{09}, a_{10}, a_{11}, \dots, a_{16}\}$, $t_3 = \{a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, \dots, a_{24}\}$, \dots , $t_n = \{a_{8n-7}, a_{8n-6}, a_{8n-5}, \dots, a_{8n}\}$. If $n \nmid 8$, then padding is done as many as k , so that it will result in (2). With $(n+k)|8$; $k = 1, 2, \dots, 7$.

$$T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n, t_{n+1}, t_{n+2}, \dots, t_{n+k}\} \quad (2)$$

The square that is used as the transposition media can be adjusted to the bit size of the text input. This research chooses 64-bit text input, so it will be a square size of 8×8 shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Square transposition 8×8

The entry scheme is a way to place each bit of a_i ; $i \in Z_{64}^+$ in the entry of square with certain rules. For example, every bit after entering into a square is the order of bits given in (3).

$$T_{sq} = \{a_1^*, a_2^*, a_3^*, \dots, a_{64}^*\} \tag{3}$$

A retrieval scheme is a way to take every bit of a_i^* , $i \in Z_{64}^+$ from the square with a certain rule. Notation for each bit taken from square ($a_{i(j)}^*$); $\exists i, j \in Z_{64}^+$ where i is the entry index and j is the retrieval index. In (4) is a schema collection dataset $L = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_8\}$, where $\exists x \in Z_{64}^+$.

$$\begin{aligned} l_1 &= \{a_{x(01)}^*, a_{x(02)}^*, a_{x(03)}^*, \dots, a_{x(08)}^*\}, \\ l_2 &= \{a_{x(09)}^*, a_{x(10)}^*, a_{x(11)}^*, \dots, a_{x(16)}^*\}, \\ &\vdots \\ l_8 &= \{a_{x(57)}^*, a_{x(58)}^*, a_{x(59)}^*, \dots, a_{x(64)}^*\}. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

2.2. Square transposition schematic testing

Every combination of input and output schemes in the square transposition will result in a transposition method, and each combination must produce a random order of index values. All users can design their input and output schemes. Therefore, random testing needs to be done to ensure that every designed scheme will produce a good transposition method.

Figure 4 shows a testing scheme, in which if each pair of schemes has not yet reached randomness, a scheme can be replaced by another scheme. This research uses three tests of randomness (Frequency Monobit Test, Frequency Test within a Block, and Runs Test) so that if two or three methods are random, the combination of those schemes can be used as a method of transposition.

Figure 4. Testing of input and output schemes

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Square transposition entry scheme

Based on (1), 64-bit is used as input and square size 8×8 . Two input schemes are selected with randomly selected index values, the two schemes are given in succession in Figures 5 and 6, respectively.

a_{37}	a_{29}	a_{18}	a_{53}	a_{47}	a_{21}	a_{27}	a_{48}
a_{30}	a_{39}	a_{41}	a_{46}	a_{22}	a_{58}	a_{05}	a_{43}
a_{23}	a_{34}	a_{42}	a_{57}	a_{40}	a_{12}	a_{64}	a_{06}
a_{11}	a_{59}	a_{16}	a_{51}	a_{63}	a_{25}	a_{45}	a_{56}
a_{24}	a_{09}	a_{26}	a_{01}	a_{20}	a_{60}	a_{03}	a_{19}
a_{54}	a_{31}	a_{49}	a_{32}	a_{04}	a_{38}	a_{15}	a_{50}
a_{17}	a_{14}	a_{08}	a_{35}	a_{44}	a_{10}	a_{33}	a_{62}
a_{61}	a_{13}	a_{02}	a_{07}	a_{36}	a_{28}	a_{52}	a_{55}

Figure 5. Input scheme 1

a_{50}	a_{24}	a_{33}	a_{06}	a_{48}	a_{09}	a_{13}	a_{25}
a_{52}	a_{44}	a_{22}	a_{58}	a_{49}	a_{15}	a_{38}	a_{51}
a_{29}	a_{07}	a_{57}	a_{20}	a_{05}	a_{43}	a_{55}	a_{10}
a_{64}	a_{14}	a_{30}	a_{39}	a_{04}	a_{27}	a_{60}	a_{11}
a_{47}	a_{01}	a_{32}	a_{62}	a_{03}	a_{37}	a_{59}	a_{23}
a_{28}	a_{63}	a_{18}	a_{54}	a_{45}	a_{36}	a_{35}	a_{12}
a_{42}	a_{31}	a_{40}	a_{61}	a_{19}	a_{02}	a_{53}	a_{26}
a_{46}	a_{16}	a_{41}	a_{17}	a_{34}	a_{56}	a_{21}	a_{08}

Figure 6. Input scheme 2

3.2. Retrieval scheme design

The retrieval scheme is a rule that takes every bit from a square that previously had a bit from the bit entry process. Here are several retrieval schemes used as pairs of input schemes.

3.2.1. Horizontal retrieval scheme

This design uses the Entry-1 Scheme to insert bits into a square, as shown in Figure 7. The horizontal retrieval process is carried out from the top left corner to the right corner of the square. The order of each bit a_{8i+1} for $i = 0, 1, \dots, 7$ is always to the left of the first entry of every line to square $(i + 1)$.

The horizontal retrieval scheme results starts from a_{37} based on the index $j = 1$ to $j = 64$ for a_{55} . Thus, square transposition output is obtained which is based on byte, as shown previously in (4), is a schema collection dataset $L = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_8\}$ where $l_1 = \{a_{37}, a_{29}, \dots, a_{48}\}$, $l_2 = \{a_{30}, a_{39}, a_{41}, \dots, a_{43}\}$, \dots , $l_8 = \{a_{61}, a_{13}, a_{02}, \dots, a_{55}\}$. Transposition results from the retrieval-1 scheme and the horizontal entry schema can be visualized in Cartesian coordinates, where each takes index (i) is abscissa and index enter (j) as ordinate. The results of complete bit retrieval are shown in Figure 8.

$a_{37}(01)$	$a_{29}(02)$	$a_{18}(03)$	$a_{53}(04)$	$a_{47}(05)$	$a_{21}(06)$	$a_{27}(07)$	$a_{48}(08)$
$a_{30}(09)$	$a_{39}(10)$	$a_{41}(11)$	$a_{46}(12)$	$a_{22}(13)$	$a_{58}(14)$	$a_{05}(15)$	$a_{43}(16)$
$a_{23}(17)$	$a_{34}(18)$	$a_{42}(19)$	$a_{57}(20)$	$a_{40}(21)$	$a_{12}(22)$	$a_{64}(23)$	$a_{06}(24)$
$a_{11}(25)$	$a_{59}(26)$	$a_{16}(27)$	$a_{51}(28)$	$a_{63}(29)$	$a_{25}(30)$	$a_{45}(31)$	$a_{56}(32)$
$a_{24}(33)$	$a_{09}(34)$	$a_{26}(35)$	$a_{01}(36)$	$a_{20}(37)$	$a_{60}(38)$	$a_{03}(39)$	$a_{19}(40)$
$a_{54}(41)$	$a_{31}(42)$	$a_{49}(43)$	$a_{32}(44)$	$a_{04}(45)$	$a_{38}(46)$	$a_{15}(47)$	$a_{50}(48)$
$a_{17}(49)$	$a_{14}(50)$	$a_{08}(51)$	$a_{35}(52)$	$a_{44}(53)$	$a_{10}(54)$	$a_{33}(55)$	$a_{62}(56)$
$a_{61}(57)$	$a_{13}(58)$	$a_{02}(59)$	$a_{07}(60)$	$a_{36}(61)$	$a_{28}(62)$	$a_{52}(63)$	$a_{55}(64)$

Figure 7. Horizontal retrieval scheme

Figure 8. Graphic of the index values

3.2.2. Vertical retrieval scheme

Square transposition also uses an input-1 scheme to input each entry from the square. Retrieval is done vertically from top to bottom, starting at the top right corner entry to the bottom right of the square. In general, every bit of $a_i(j)$ and the retrieval index $j = (8z + 1)$; $z \in \{0, 1, \dots, 7\}$. If z is even, the retrieval is done vertically top-down, and if z is odd, the retrieval will be done from the bottom up. The retrieval results are based on bits shown in Figure 9.

The vertical retrieval scheme starts from a_{48} based on the index $j = 1$ to $j = 64$ for a_{37} bits. So the square transposition output is based on bytes $L = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_8\}$, where $l_1 = \{a_{48}, a_{43}, a_{06}, \dots, a_{55}\}$, $l_2 = \{a_{52}, a_{33}, a_{15}, \dots, a_{27}\}$, \dots , $l_8 = \{a_{61}, a_{17}, a_{54}, \dots, a_{37}\}$. The visualization of transposition index of the input-1 scheme and the vertical input scheme is shown in Figure 10.

$a_{37}(64)$	$a_{29}(49)$	$a_{18}(48)$	$a_{53}(33)$	$a_{47}(32)$	$a_{21}(17)$	$a_{27}(16)$	$a_{48}(01)$
$a_{30}(63)$	$a_{39}(50)$	$a_{41}(47)$	$a_{46}(34)$	$a_{22}(31)$	$a_{58}(18)$	$a_{05}(15)$	$a_{43}(02)$
$a_{23}(62)$	$a_{34}(51)$	$a_{42}(46)$	$a_{57}(35)$	$a_{40}(30)$	$a_{12}(19)$	$a_{64}(14)$	$a_{06}(03)$
$a_{11}(61)$	$a_{59}(52)$	$a_{16}(45)$	$a_{51}(36)$	$a_{63}(29)$	$a_{25}(20)$	$a_{45}(13)$	$a_{56}(04)$
$a_{24}(60)$	$a_{09}(53)$	$a_{26}(44)$	$a_{01}(37)$	$a_{20}(28)$	$a_{60}(21)$	$a_{03}(12)$	$a_{19}(05)$
$a_{54}(59)$	$a_{31}(54)$	$a_{49}(43)$	$a_{32}(38)$	$a_{04}(27)$	$a_{38}(22)$	$a_{15}(11)$	$a_{50}(06)$
$a_{17}(58)$	$a_{14}(55)$	$a_{08}(42)$	$a_{35}(39)$	$a_{44}(26)$	$a_{10}(23)$	$a_{33}(10)$	$a_{62}(07)$
$a_{61}(57)$	$a_{13}(56)$	$a_{02}(41)$	$a_{07}(40)$	$a_{36}(25)$	$a_{28}(24)$	$a_{52}(09)$	$a_{55}(08)$

Figure 9. Vertical Retrieval Scheme

Figure 10. Graphic of the index values

3.2.3. Zigzag retrieval scheme

The input-2 scheme is used in Figure 6 which the retrieval scheme is done in zigzag form from the lower left to the upper right. The retrieval plots are based on index values $j = 1$ to $j = 64$, which the

complete plots are shown in Figure 11. Retrieval starts from a_{46} to a_{25} , so that the square transposition output can be obtained based on byte $L = \{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_8\}$ where $l_1 = \{a_{46}, a_{42}, a_{16}, \dots, a_{63}\}$, $l_2 = \{a_{40}, a_{17}, a_{64}, \dots, a_{29}\}$, \dots $l_8 = \{a_5, a_{11}, a_{09}, \dots, a_{25}\}$. The geometric interpretation of the value of the zigzag input-2 and zigzag retrieval scheme is shown in Figure 12.

$a_{50}(29)$	$a_{24}(37)$	$a_{33}(44)$	$a_{06}(50)$	$a_{48}(55)$	$a_{09}(59)$	$a_{13}(62)$	$a_{25}(64)$
$a_{52}(22)$	$a_{44}(30)$	$a_{22}(38)$	$a_{58}(45)$	$a_{49}(51)$	$a_{15}(56)$	$a_{38}(60)$	$a_{51}(63)$
$a_{29}(16)$	$a_{07}(23)$	$a_{57}(31)$	$a_{20}(39)$	$a_{05}(46)$	$a_{43}(52)$	$a_{55}(57)$	$a_{10}(61)$
$a_{64}(11)$	$a_{14}(17)$	$a_{30}(24)$	$a_{39}(32)$	$a_{04}(40)$	$a_{27}(47)$	$a_{60}(53)$	$a_{11}(58)$
$a_{47}(07)$	$a_{01}(12)$	$a_{32}(18)$	$a_{62}(25)$	$a_{03}(33)$	$a_{37}(41)$	$a_{59}(48)$	$a_{23}(54)$
$a_{28}(04)$	$a_{63}(08)$	$a_{18}(13)$	$a_{54}(19)$	$a_{45}(26)$	$a_{36}(34)$	$a_{35}(42)$	$a_{12}(49)$
$a_{42}(02)$	$a_{31}(05)$	$a_{40}(09)$	$a_{61}(14)$	$a_{19}(20)$	$a_{02}(27)$	$a_{53}(35)$	$a_{26}(43)$
$a_{46}(01)$	$a_{16}(03)$	$a_{41}(06)$	$a_{17}(10)$	$a_{34}(15)$	$a_{56}(21)$	$a_{21}(28)$	$a_{08}(36)$

Figure 11. Zigzag retrieval scheme

Figure 12. Graphic of the index values

3.2.4. Rice plow retrieval scheme

The transposition technique by adopting the rice plow process can be done with the assumption of a square as a rice field plot. Each bit plot is adjusted to the rice plow process starting from the outside point towards the midpoint, which the complete plots are shown in Figure 13. The input-2 scheme is used to fill in each input from the square so that the retrieval using rice plow plot can be carried out.

The retrieval process starts from the lower right corner (a_{08}) with a rotating plot around the square towards the center (a_{04}). The value of the transposition output index of the input-2 scheme and rice scheme retrieval is $L = \{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_8\}$; where $l_1 = \{a_{08}, a_{21}, a_{56}, \dots, a_{46}\}$, $l_2 = \{a_{42}, a_{28}, a_{47}, \dots, a_{24}\}$, \dots $l_8 = \{a_{43}, a_{43}, a_{27}, \dots, a_{04}\}$. The visualization of the transposition index value is shown in Figure 14.

$a_{50}(15)$	$a_{24}(16)$	$a_{33}(17)$	$a_{06}(18)$	$a_{48}(19)$	$a_{09}(20)$	$a_{13}(21)$	$a_{25}(22)$
$a_{52}(14)$	$a_{44}(39)$	$a_{22}(40)$	$a_{58}(41)$	$a_{49}(42)$	$a_{15}(43)$	$a_{38}(44)$	$a_{51}(23)$
$a_{29}(13)$	$a_{07}(38)$	$a_{57}(55)$	$a_{20}(56)$	$a_{05}(57)$	$a_{43}(58)$	$a_{55}(45)$	$a_{10}(24)$
$a_{64}(12)$	$a_{14}(37)$	$a_{30}(54)$	$a_{39}(63)$	$a_{04}(64)$	$a_{27}(59)$	$a_{60}(46)$	$a_{11}(25)$
$a_{47}(11)$	$a_{01}(36)$	$a_{32}(53)$	$a_{62}(62)$	$a_{03}(61)$	$a_{37}(60)$	$a_{59}(47)$	$a_{23}(26)$
$a_{28}(10)$	$a_{63}(35)$	$a_{18}(52)$	$a_{54}(51)$	$a_{45}(50)$	$a_{36}(49)$	$a_{35}(48)$	$a_{12}(27)$
$a_{42}(09)$	$a_{31}(34)$	$a_{40}(33)$	$a_{61}(32)$	$a_{19}(31)$	$a_{02}(30)$	$a_{53}(29)$	$a_{26}(28)$
$a_{46}(08)$	$a_{16}(07)$	$a_{41}(06)$	$a_{17}(05)$	$a_{34}(04)$	$a_{56}(03)$	$a_{21}(02)$	$a_{08}(01)$

Figure 13. Rice plow retrieval scheme

Figure 14. Graphic of the index values

3.3. Testing of randomness on index values

The method used in randomness testing is Mono Bit frequency Test, Bit Block frequency Test, and Run Test, with $\alpha = 0.01$. Each transposition index value is declared as random if two or three test results

have p -value $> \alpha$. The complete test results are shown in Table 1. The combination of each input scheme and retrieval scheme is carried out to see how well the pair of schemes are designed or selected so that square transposition can produce a random index value.

The schemes of input 1 & vertical output obtain the highest p -value with the average value of 0.273, and the ones with the lowest score are the schemes of input 1 & zigzag scheme with a smaller average of p -value, which is 0.101. Overall, all pairs of input and output schemes can maintain the p -value that results in a random index value and the pair of schemes can produce a better index value when compared to the transposition method in AES and DES algorithms.

Table 1. Randomness test result for each scheme

2*No	2*Input & Retrieval Scheme	p -value			2*Result
		Mono Bit	Block Bit	Run-Test	
1	Input-1 & Horizontal Scheme	0.1341	0.1230	0.1853	random
2	Input-1 & Vertical Scheme	0.2727	0.2194	0.1432	random
3	Input-2 & Zigzag Scheme	0.1204	0.2282	0.2031	random
4	Input-2 & Rice Plow Scheme	0.1950	0.1917	0.1981	random
5	Input-1 & Zigzag Scheme	0.1012	0.1118	0.2116	random
6	Input-1 & Rice Plow Scheme	0.1018	0.2014	0.1102	random
7	Input-2 & Horizontal Scheme	0.1210	0.1052	0.2056	random
8	Input-2 & Vertical Scheme	0.2044	0.2015	0.1186	random
9	DES	2.569×10^{-8}	0.0539	9.172×10^{-6}	non random
10	AES	4.251×10^{-8}	0.0042	1.456×10^{-4}	non random

The use of output-1 and output-2 schemes plays an important role in yielding the output of random index values. Selection of a pair of schemes using a combination of horizontal, vertical, zigzag, and plow or others that have a patterned index will generate poor transposition index value. It happens because the input and output scheme has the same or similar line direction.

3.4. Correlation testing

Correlation value (r) can be used to see the magnitude of the relationship between input (x) and output (y) of statistically related algorithms. The correlation interval is $-1 \leq r \leq 1$, and if r approaches 0, then the algorithm is able to make the input and output not statistically related. In this condition, if $r < 0$, the absolute value $|r|$ can be used to find out the distance r from 0.

Correlation testing uses three plaintext inputs which it is expected to represent text variations that might be used by users. Input “fti uksw” is to represent traditional text input because usually, users use it. The second more extreme test is the use of the same input, which is “xyyyyyyyy” (not “yyyyyyyyy” because this correlation formula is undefined). The third test is “\$aL4t1G4” which also represents a variety of symbols, numbers, and letters that are used as input.

The results obtained in Table 2 show that the output of each scheme of the square transposition has an average correlation value close to 0. Thus, it indicates that the relationship between input and output is not related statistically. Consequently, the square transposition succeeds in disguising the information, so that the distribution of redundancies occurs well and will certainly increase the diffusion effect on the cryptography algorithm.

Table 2. Testing result of input-output correlation

2*No	2*Transposition Method	Correlation Value $ r $			2*Average
		fti uksw	xyyyyyyy	\$aL4t1G4	
1	Input-1 & Horizontal Retrieval	0.249	0.331	0.217	0.266
2	Input-1 & Vertical Retrieval	0.162	0.127	0.142	0.162
3	Input-2 & Zigzag Retrieval	0.254	0.267	0.324	0.254
4	Input-2 & Rice Plow Retrieval	0.313	0.375	0.252	0.313
5	Input-1 & Zigzag Retrieval	0.112	0.009	0.018	0.112
6	Input-1 & Rice Plow Retrieval	0.016	0.090	0.040	0.016
7	Input-2 & Horizontal Retrieval	0.138	0.268	0.265	0.138
8	Input-2 & Vertical Retrieval	0.076	0.098	0.184	0.076
9	DES	0.342	0.126	0.374	0.342
10	AES	0.376	0.429	0.277	0.376

The transposition of DES and AES algorithms has resulted in higher average correlation values than the value from the schematic combination of square transposition so that it can be said that each pair of schemes can generate a better transposition algorithm. Of course, the use of square transposition in cryptography will increase the strength of overall cryptographic algorithms. Optimization of the transposition process using square transposition is a part that needs to be done by cryptographers to improve or modify the weak parts of the algorithm.

4. CONCLUSION

The determination of a pair of input and output schemes in square transposition should be based on schemes that have different lines to obtain a good transposition process. Combination of schemes that were carried out produced less patterned geometric visualization that oscillates irregularly, so that the transposition method could generate random index values. This result is also seen in randomness testing in which the overall obtained p-value is greater which $\alpha = 1\%$ so that the square transposition can produce better a transposition method when it is compared to AES and DES values which the index is not random. Square transposition produces an average correlation value closer to 0 for testing the text input when compared to AES and DES transpositions. Thus, the square transposition manages to disguise the information on the input so that it is not visible in the output. Besides, the square transposition can spread the distributed redundancies well, so that it will increase the diffusion effect on the cryptographic algorithm. The result shows that the algorithm in the square transposition optimizes the transposition process that previously has non-random index values. This design optimizes algorithm processes by concentrating on the diffusion effect and by not giving a burden on the complexity of time and space. Algorithm modification is a process that every cryptographer needs to do to produce a more efficient algorithm in cryptography to secure information.

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